

THE TEXT OF A LETTER AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS AND ITS GENRE CHARACTERISTICS

Ashurova Muxayyoxon Sanjarbek qizi

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098977>

Abstract. *This article examines the meaning and use of the text of a letter as an important and integral part of the communication process, as well as the genre characteristics of the text of a letter. Examples of the text of letters in English and Uzbek languages are given, and their similarities and differences are analyzed.*

Keywords: *information, e-mail, text messages communication, addresser, addressee, internet.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается значение и использование текста письма как важной и неотъемлемой части процесса общения, а также жанровые характеристики текста письма. Приводятся примеры текста писем на английском и узбекском языках, анализируются их сходства и различия.*

Ключевые слова: *информация, электронная почта, текстовые сообщения общение, адресат, адресант, интернет.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada xat matnining kommunikatsiya jarayonining muhim va ajralmas qismi sifatidagi ahamiyati va qo'llanilishi, shuningdek, xat matnining janr xususiyatlari haqida so'z yuritiladi. Ingliz va O'zbek tillaridagi tillardagi xatlar matniga misollar keltirilib, ulardagi o'xshashlik va farqli jihatlari tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *axborot, elektron pochta, matnli xabarlar, kommunikatsiya, adresat, adresant, internet.*

INTRODUCTION. The word "Xat" in Arabic is a written text sent from one person to another, containing certain information. This word is also referred to as "maktub", "noma", which has the same meaning as above. [3, 225]

A letter is one of the integral parts of the communication process and is used as the main means of exchanging information and expressing one's thoughts between people. Letters are delivered in written form and provide an exchange of information between the addresser and the addressee through a response or answer to them.

Letters are usually delivered in writing, but nowadays can also be sent via e-mail, text messages, or Internet chats. Letters are considered an important tool for strengthening communication between people. Text communication includes creating, delivering, presenting and receiving a message, detailing and supporting.

MAIN PART. The letter is one of the first inventions of mankind, and after the appearance of writing, it served as the main type of interpersonal communication and continues to do so. As a means of communication, letters are sent and received by mail, telegraph, fax, and the Internet. Such letters are called personal letters. Letters that are of interest to society at one level or another and are important are valued as letters of social significance. Such letters are delivered to the masses through written literature and journalism. Such letters, which reflect facts, events and incidents in one or another sphere of society, give some news to the public opinion, and arouse thoughts, are also related to publicism and journalism. That is, a person informs about any facts, events, events in life through the means of journalism, expresses his opinion about them, or asks

for help on any issue, complains and etc. Therefore, a letter is an important tool that connects a person with society and, in turn, society with a person [3, 226].

The communicative features of the text of the letter are reflected in the following:

1. Language and style: the text of the letter reflects the language and style of writing. This feature ensures that the writing is received and understood.

2. Content: The information and ideas conveyed in the text of the letter are distinguished by the importance of the content. It is important that the content is accurate and clear.

3. Literacy: The text of the letter should follow the rules of literature. It includes language, style, manner of speaking and other literary features.

4. Discussion: The text of the letter should clearly show the presence of discussion and debate skills. This provides an opportunity to establish two-way communication and exchange ideas.

5. Confirmation or denial: The text of the letter should contain elements necessary to confirm and support or deny the ideas and information.

These features determine the communicative characteristics of the text of the letter and provide the content, purpose and discussion possibilities of the writing.

It is known that all types of letters serve to establish a communicative relationship between the participants of the dialogue: the addresser and the addressee. Even in cases where there is no requirement to respond to letters, the addressee enters into a secret communication with the addresser who sends it through the letter, that is, he becomes aware of a certain message or gets some information through the letter. In such a situation, a communication environment, a speech situation occurs between the addresser, that is, the sender of the letter and the receiver-addressee [6, 83].

In particular, informational letters serve to inform the addressee about the event or conference being held or to deliver a message to him as information. In this situation, the addresser and the addressee enter into a communicative relationship by means of an information letter: one sends a message, the other receives it.

The communicative function of the text of letters is clarified through communicative effectiveness. When letters are answered, explanations are given, or instructions and recommendations specified in the letter are followed, requests or assignments are fulfilled, communicative tasks are achieved through letters. Communicative effectiveness can be achieved through letters written in a short, clear and fluent style, in compliance with language norms [6, 84].

There can be different genres of letters and some of them are:

- Official letters: Letters written by government, business or other official organizations. They can usually be formal in style and pictorial:

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Shavkat Mirziyoyev janobi oliylariga

Janobi Oliylari, Sizni O'zbekiston

Respublikasi Mustaqilligining 27 yillik

bayrami bilan muborakbod etishga ijozat

bergaysiz. O'zbekiston Respublikasi xalqiga

bundan buyon ham ravnaq, baxt-saodat va

farovonlik tilayman.

Dear Mr. President-Elect:

Please accept my warm

congratulations on your victory and my best

wishes for your success as you prepare to

take up the responsibilities and challenges of

your high office...

I look forward to working with you

not only to develop closer relations between

our countries but also to concert our efforts

*Yelizaveta Ikkinchi. Buyuk Britaniya in the cause of peace and the brotherhood of
va Shimoliy Irlandiya Birlashgan Qirolligi all peoples.
Qirolichasi. Sincerely, RICHARD NIXON.*

- Informal letters: Letters exchanged between friends or relatives. They can usually be written in an informal style, including emojis or fun text colors.

*Dear John,
Hope you are safe and protected. It's
been a long time since we last met. I have
been quite busy recently. I had a day off from
work today and so decided to write a letter to
you asking about you and your family.*

*I am fine here. I have recently started
learning French and have completed a few
modules. Next week I am taking the last exam
and will be soon graduating. I also started
cooking due to the lockdown and will be
attaching a few pictures of the dishes I
learned to cook Mom and Dad are fine and
they quite often miss you.*

*Lots of Love
Angela.*

*Qadrdonim Nigora,
Sen bilan ko'rishmaganimizga ham
bir oydan oshdi. Yozgi ta'tilingni bobongning
qishlog'ida yaxshi o'tkizyapsanmi? Shahar
hayotini sog'ingandursan. Seni juda ham
sog'indim. Kelasi hafta men ham qishloqqa
boraman va sen bilan ko'rishaman.*

Eng yaqin do'sting,

- Business letters: Letters exchanged between employees within businesses or organizations. They are usually written in a formal style and for the purpose of sharing information.

Dear Calista Merritt,

*I am writing this letter to inform you about the Liberal Arts department workshop which is
going to be held on April 19th, 2019. With this workshop, the employees under the Liberal Arts
department will have the opportunity to interact with important business leaders in our locality.*

*This workshop will be conducted at the Plaza Student Center at Delhi University. This
event will start from 10 a.m. and will last for 3-4 hours. A table can be reserved for the interested
employees before the workshop upon doing the registration.*

Thank you for your time and hoping to hear from you sooner.

*Sincerely,
Zephaniah Sanders*

- Promotional letters: Letters written for the purpose of advertising products or services. They can usually be for performance style and presentation purposes.

Dear Edward Nieves,

*This is to state that you are offered the role of Senior Manager in DigitalSoft Technologies.
The compensation amount will be 15, 23456 INR which is as per market standards. If you accept
this offer we will start our joining process on 01st Dec 2015 and your offered salary will be
effective from the same date.*

Please write us back on your decision. We will be waiting for your positive response.

*Sincerely,
Imani Talley*

Complaint letters: Complaints or suggestions sent by customers to organizations. They should be written in a formal and acceptable style to be acceptable.

Dear Mr. Brown,

I am writing on behalf of my son, Bob, who is on the local baseball team. He has told me, and I have observed, that on numerous occasions during the current baseball season, he has been unfairly excluded from fully participating in baseball games and activities. Needless to say, this has created some serious interpersonal and confidence issues for Bob.

Please call me as soon as possible at 383-3829 so that we can discuss this issue and determine the best way to resolve this. Thanks for your time and for working with us to create a positive outcome for this situation.

Sincerely,

Jane White.

• Letters of Execution: Letters written as a style of execution. They are written appropriately and used for practices.

Dear Sir.

We thank you for your order No. p-3-7 dated September 1, 2012 for various paints. The order is in the process of execution and it will be dispatched on 8th September, by our Motor van. We have taken special care for the quality and packing of the paints and we hope that you will find them highly satisfactory.

We thank you again for your kind offer of the paints and hope that you -will extend your similar co-operation in the future.

With best regards

Yours faithfully

A K Rahman

Sales Manager

Each type of letter has its own characteristics and goals. Letters can have different characteristics according to the cover, purpose, discussion and reception processes of writing and text.

CONCLUSION. As can be seen from the above information, letters are one of the integral parts of the communication process and are used as one of the main means of exchanging information and expressing one's thoughts between people. So, based on the analysis of the communicative and genre features of the text of letters, which are an important means of communication between people, the following conclusions can be summarized:

- The text of official letters provides a communicative connection between the participants of the speech, that is, the addresser and the addressee, creates a communication environment, a speech situation;
- The text of official letters will have a sign of communicative effectiveness;
- Communicative features of letters provide the content, purpose and discussion possibilities of the text of the letter;
- Letters can have different characteristics according to the cover, purpose, discussion and acceptance processes of writing and text;
- Each letter genre has its own characteristics and goals.

REFERENCES

1. Jo'rayev T. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tilida epistolyar janrning til va uslubiy xususiyatlari. nomzodlik dissertasiyasi. – Samarqand,1994.
2. Mahmudov N., Rafiyev A., Yo'ldoshev I. Davlat tilida ish yuritish. – Toshkent,2004.
3. Qozoqboyev T., Xudoyqulov M. Jurnalistikaga kirish. – Toshkent,2018.
4. Safarov Sh. Pragmalingvistika. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi , 2008.
5. Каримов Р. Тижорат хатларининг лингвопрагматик аспекти: Филол.фан бўйича фалс. Док.(PhD) дисс. афтореф. – Тошкент,2018.
6. Лутфуллаева Д. Мустақиллик даври расмий-идоравий иш услуби таракқиёти. – Тошкент,2020.
7. Мухиддинова Х.С., Абдуллаева Н.А. Расмий услубнинг дипломатик ёзишмалар тури. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон Республикаси Халқ таълими вазирлиги Республика таълим маркази, 1997.
8. LINGVOPRAGMATIKA SOHASINING PAYDO BO'LISHI, RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI VA O'RGANISH OBYEKTI. M Ashurova - Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi, 2023 - research-edu.com
9. bestlettertemplate.com
10. www.wikipedia.org
11. www.wordtemplatesonline.net